

TRAINING YOUNG RESEARCHERS ON SHAPING METAVERSE
FOR BUSINESS AND SOCIAL VALUE

DC14 – INTERVIEW GUIDE

INTERVIEW GUIDE SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS ON COMPLEMENTOR INFLUENCE ON DIGITAL RESPONSIBILITY IN METAVERSE PLATFORM BUSINESS MODELS

Estimated Duration: 60-90 minutes

Introduction (5 minutes)

- Thank the participant for their time
- Recap research purpose: understanding how complementors like themselves influence platform decisions and practices, particularly regarding responsibility
- Confirm consent and permission to record
- Emphasise confidentiality and anonymisation
- Explain interview structure and invite questions

PART 1: Background and Platform Engagement (10-15 minutes)

1. Can you tell me about your role as a complementor on?
 - a. How long have you been creating/developing on this platform?
 - b. What type of content/products/services do you provide?
2. What motivated you to become a complementor on this platform?
 - a. What attracted you to this platform specifically?
3. How would you describe your relationship with the platform?
 - a. Do you work exclusively on this platform or multiple platforms?
 - b. How important is this platform to your overall work/income?

PART 2: Complementor Influence Mechanisms (20-25 minutes)

4. Have you ever tried to influence or change something about how the platform operates?
 - a. Can you describe a specific example?
 - b. What prompted you to take this action?
5. How do you typically communicate your needs or concerns to the platform?
 - a. Are there formal channels (forums, support, feedback systems)?
 - b. Do you use informal channels (direct contacts, social media)?
 - c. Which channels seem most effective?
6. Have you ever participated in collective action with other participants that do similar things as you do on the platform?
 - a. Can you describe what happened and what the outcome was?
 - b. How did you organize or coordinate?
7. How would you describe your ability to influence platform decisions?
 - a. In what areas do you feel you have more or less influence?
 - b. What factors determine whether your influence attempts succeed?
8. Can you think of a time when the platform changed something because of your or others' feedback?
 - a. What changed and how did it happen?
 - b. Who was involved in pushing for this change?

PART 3: Digital Responsibility Perceptions (20-25 minutes)

9. What does "responsible business practices" mean to you in the context of this metaverse platform?
 - a. What specific issues or practices come to mind?

10. What responsibilities do you think the platform owner should have toward partners/developers like yourself?
 - a. Are there specific areas where you feel the platform should do more?
 - b. Can you give examples of where the platform handles this responsibility well or poorly?
11. Do you think partners/developers like yourself have responsibilities when they share their work on the metaverse platform?
 - a. What are those responsibilities?
 - b. Do you see yourself as having a role in making the metaverse more responsible?
12. Which responsibility issues matter most to you? [If needed, offer examples: data privacy, fair compensation, content moderation, accessibility, environmental impact]
 - a. Why are these particularly important to you?
 - b. How do these issues affect your work?
13. Have you ever tried to influence the platform on responsibility-related issues?
 - a. What issue and what did you do?
 - b. What was the platform's response?

PART 4: Influence and Responsibility Integration (15-20 minutes)

14. Thinking about the areas where individuals or companies like you/yours can influence the platform, which areas do you think are most important for ensuring the platform operates responsibly?
 - a. Platform policies? Technical infrastructure? Revenue models? Governance structures?
15. In your experience, when developers/platform partners push for changes, do responsibility concerns factor into those efforts?
 - a. Can you give an example?
 - b. Do you think you developers and platforms have similar or different views on what's responsible?
16. If you could change one thing about how the platform handles responsibility, what would it be?
 - a. Do you think developers/platform partners could play a role in making that change happen?
17. How do you see your role evolving in relation to platform governance and responsibility?
 - a. Do you expect to have more or less influence over time?

Closing (5 minutes)

18. Is there anything else about your experience as a developer or about platform responsibility that you think is important for me to understand?
19. Do you have any questions for me about the research?

Thank the participant and confirm anonymisation preferences